

THE EFFECT OF PARTICLE SIZE IN ALUMINA NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The effect of particle size in composites was investigated using alumina particles in an epoxy vinyl ester resin. Three different particle sizes were used: 40 nm, 1 μm and 3 μm . The particles were dispersed via sonication. The resulting suspensions had viscosities much higher than predicted by micromechanics perhaps because of ionic associations between particles and polymer molecules. The smallest particles yielded the highest viscosity. The dielectric constant of suspension also increased with decreasing particle size. The moduli of the cured composites were fairly insensitive to the particle size, yet much higher than micromechanics predictions. However, the strength decreased with the addition of particles. The nonuniformity of particle size distribution and the particle agglomeration are believed to be at least partially responsible for the observed decrease in composite strength.

Keywords: alumina composites, polymer nanocomposites, dielectric properties, suspension viscosity, mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

Micron-size particles have been used to increase the moduli of composites. However, one of the drawbacks is that such improvements usually come at the sacrifice of ductility. Nevertheless, it has been shown that while the fracture toughness and modulus remain fairly independent of the particle size, the flexural strength may increase as the particle size decreases. Furthermore, even the tensile failure strain can be increased by adding nanoparticles [1]. Therefore, the main purpose of the present paper is to investigate the effect of particle size into the nanometer range.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

The matrix resin used was Derakane 411-350, which is an epoxy vinyl ester resin manufactured by The Dow Chemical Company. In liquid state, it has a density of 1.045 g/cm^3 and a viscosity of 350 cps at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The particles used are aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) of three different nominal diameters: 3 μm , 1 μm and 40 nm. The densities of 3- μm and 1- μm particles were reported by the suppliers to be 3.9 g/cm^3 , whereas the density of the 40-nm particles was 3.6 g/cm^3 . Curing was achieved by addition of Trigonox 239 A catalyst and cobalt naphthenate (CoNap) promoter.

Composite Fabrication

Aluminum oxide particles were weighed to provide the desired volume fraction and mixed in 100 ml of vinyl ester resin. Three different fiber volume fractions were used: 1, 2, and 3%. Mixing was accomplished by sonication using a 20-kHz ultrasonic horn at a power level of 24W for one hour. The

suspension was stirred constantly in a container immersed in running water at room temperature to keep the temperature from becoming too high during sonication.

After sonication the suspension was vacuumed for an hour to remove air bubbles introduced during mixing. The suspension was cured by adding 2% of Trigonox, and 0.3% of CoNap. The cured composite was postured for one hour at 85°C.

Rheological Properties

The neat resin and suspensions were tested for viscosity at 25° C on a Haake RT 10 cup and cone viscometer using a shear rate sweep. The results are shown in Figs. 1 through 3.

Figure 1. Viscosities of neat resins and suspensions.

The neat resin is seen to be fairly Newtonian as it does not show much dependence on the shear rate. With increasing particle loading, however, the behavior changes from Newtonian to non-Newtonian exhibiting shear thinning.

It was found in an earlier study [2] that the viscosities of iron oxide suspensions could be described by a Bingham model as

$$\eta = \eta_p + \frac{\tau_o}{\dot{\gamma}} \quad (1)$$

where η_p is the plastic viscosity, τ_o is the yield stress, and $\dot{\gamma}$ is the shear rate. However, Fig. 1 indicates that the Bingham model is not appropriate for the alumina suspensions.

As the particle loading increases so does the viscosity. At the same particle loading, the

smallest particles (40 nm) yield the highest viscosity and the largest particles (3 μ m) the lowest viscosity.

For large particles, the Einstein theory predicts that the viscosity η of a suspension with a particle volume fraction V_p is given by [3]

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_m} = 1 + \frac{5}{2} V_p \quad (2)$$

Thus, for 1-vol% particle loading, the suspension viscosity is expected to increase very little, only 2.5%. However, the observed increase is much more.

The addition of fine fillers, such as calcium carbonate, clay and magnesium oxide, to a polyester or vinyl ester resin is known to increase the suspension viscosity more than predicted by Eq. (2) [4, 5]. It has been proposed in [4, 5] that the thickening induced by the addition of a Group IIA metal oxide is the result of ionic associations between the carboxylic anions and the magnesium cations. A similar mechanism may exist between the fine alumina particles with surface charges and the polar carboxylic groups of the resin. The net effect is similar to that of chain extension and branching. The effective chain extension and branching due to the presence of nanoparticles increases the viscosity. The shear thinning behavior is explained by the breaking of ionic associations as the shear rate increases.

Dielectric Properties of Liquid Resin and Suspensions

Dielectric properties of suspensions were measured using an Agilent 4263B LCR Meter and a liquid test fixture 16452A. The fixture has two circular electrodes of 38-mm diameter each separated at a gap of 0.5 mm, requiring an approximate liquid volume of 3.8 ml. Capacitance C_p and resistance R_p were measured at 5 frequencies: 0.1, 0.12, 1, 10, and 100 kHz, and the data were converted to the dielectric constant ϵ_r' and the dielectric loss ϵ_r'' as follows:

$$\epsilon_r' = \frac{t * C_p}{A * \epsilon_o}, \quad \epsilon_r'' = \frac{t}{\omega * R_p * \epsilon_o * A}, \quad \epsilon_o = \frac{t * C_o}{A} \quad (3)$$

Here t =electrode gap, A =electrode area, C_o =air capacitance value (measured), and ω =angular frequency.

The dielectric constants shown in Fig. 2 increases with increasing particle loading with the increase being more for smaller particles. The dielectric constant of the neat resin is about 4.5 while that of bulk alumina is reported to be 9. The simple rule of mixtures for parallel connection thus predicts a dielectric constant of 4.55 and 4.64 for 1 vol% and 3 vol%, respectively. However, the measured values are much higher especially for the 40-nm particles while the other larger particles are not as effective, at both test frequencies. There is thus a strong indication of a synergistic effect for dielectric constant when nanoparticles are used.

The corresponding dielectric losses are shown in Fig. 3. They also increase with increasing particle loading. The size effect becomes more prominent at the high frequency as the dielectric losses are controlled by the particle mobility. As expected, the dielectric losses are much higher at the low frequency than at the high frequency.

Figure 2. Dielectric constants of liquid resin and suspensions

Figure 3. Dielectric losses of liquid resin and suspensions

Dielectric Properties of Cured Resin and Composites

Dielectric properties of solid specimens were measured on the same LCR meter using an Agilent 16451B dielectric test fixture. The fixture is equipped with an electrode type B (5mm guarded/guard electrode) for contact measurement. The specimen was a 1-cm x 1-cm square with 3-mm thickness. The specimen was sanded slightly on both contacting surfaces and then coated with a conductive silver paint.

Figure 4 shows the dielectric constants of solid composites not changing much with the addition of nanoparticles. The parallel rule of mixtures yields only a negligible amount of increase even at the maximum particle loading of 3%. Thus, the observed results are not surprising.

Figure 4. Dielectric constants of solids resin and composites

Mechanical Properties

The modulus and strength were measured in 3-point bending on an Instron model 4483 with a 900-N load cell. Each specimen was 12.7 mm wide, 3 mm thick and 70 mm long. The span to thickness ratio was kept constant at 16:1.

Figure 5. Mechanical properties

The modulus is seen to increase rather rapidly with increasing particle loading. A micromechanics model predicts the composite modulus E to increase as [6]

$$\frac{E}{E_m} = 1 + 3V_p \quad (4)$$

The above equation is valid for the cases where $E_p / E_m \gg 1$ and $V_p \ll 1$. At $V_p = 3\%$, the equation shows only 9% increase in modulus. The observed moduli are, however, much higher than predicted regardless of the particle size.

The strength does not fare as well: it does not increase with increasing particle loading. Composite specimens were found to be more brittle than neat resin specimens, resulting in lower strengths in spite of their higher moduli.

It was reported that TiO_2 nanoparticles could increase modulus without sacrifice of ductility [6]. The present results do not support the same conclusion. However, such difference could be explained as follows. First, the particle size distribution was not uniform. Transmission electron micrographs of Fig. 6 show a fairly large distribution of particle size. As failure is initiated at the weakest point, the presence of any large particles may lead to premature failure. Even when all particles are of uniform size, their agglomeration may act as a large particle. A cursory examination of fracture surfaces has revealed that failure was usually initiated at particle agglomeration sites, Fig. 7. Therefore, the possibility of synergistic effect of nanoparticles on strength cannot be ruled out yet.

Figure 6. Transmission electron micrographs of 40-nm alumina particles

CONCLUSIONS

Nanoparticles increase the suspension viscosity more than their micron-size counterparts. The reason is believed to be ionic associations between particles and resin molecules. Such interactions increase the effective chain length and branching, and hence the viscosity.

(a) 40-nm alumina

(b) 3- μ m alumina

Figure 7. Fracture surfaces

Nanoparticles are also more effective in improving the dielectric constant of suspension. The main reason appears to be the ease with which nanoparticles can align themselves readily in the field direction. The observation that the corresponding improvements in solid composites are much lower than in suspensions indicates that the shorter interparticle spacing has little effect on dielectric constants.

The observed modulus increase is rather insensitive to the particle size although it is much more than predicted by micromechanics. The reason for such higher-than-expected modulus is not clear. The strength decreases slightly as the composite becomes more brittle with the addition of particles. The poor strengths observed are believed to be the result of nonuniform particle size distribution and particle agglomeration.

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